

Preparation of Perhalogenated Unsymmetrical Biaryls *via* Perhaloarylcopper Reagents and Perfluoro- or Perchloroiodoarenes

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Several perhalogenated unsymmetrical biaryls have been prepared by coupling perhaloarylcopper reagents with perfluoro- and perchloroaryl iodides in high boiling ethers. These coupling reactions are accompanied by copper-iodine exchange reactions. IR and mass spectral data for the unsymmetrical biaryls are reported.

THE coupling reaction between an arylcopper¹ and an iodoarene to produce the corresponding unsymmetrical biaryl²⁻⁸ (eq. 1) is complicated⁸⁻¹⁰ by some competing side reactions. These are thermal decomposition of the arylcopper to produce the symmetrical biaryl⁸ (eq. 2) and copper-iodine exchange to form a new arylcopper and a new iodoarene⁸⁻¹⁰ (eq. 3). Furthermore the new copper compound and the new iodoarene react to produce a symmetrical biaryl by a reaction of the type 4.

Solvents have a profound effect on the course of these reactions. For example, a good complexing solvent is known^{8,9} to facilitate reactions 1 and 3 and reduce the participation of reactions of type 2. On the other hand, a poor complexing solvent increases^{8,9} the relative importance of reaction 2. However, the position of equilibrium of the copper-iodine exchange (eq. 3) would be dependent on the thermodynamic stabilities of the species involved.

In connection with studies on the synthesis of thermally stable polyfunctional monomer compounds⁸⁻¹² some perhalogenated unsymmetrical biaryls were required. We decided to prepare these *via* reaction 1 and at the same time examine whether or not halogen substitution in the aromatic nucleus had any influence on the relative importance of the side reactions 2 and 3. This paper is concerned with the details of this investigation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the various perhalogenated unsymmetrical biaryls (I-VI) prepared *via* reaction 1. The coupling reaction is conducted between 100-110°

in high boiling ethers such as dioxan or 2,2,4,4-tetramethyltetrahydrofuran. At lower temperatures the reaction is either very slow (*e.g.*, in refluxing THF) or does not occur at all (*e.g.*, in refluxing diethyl ether). This contrasts with the relatively low temperatures (25-50°) employed for the coupling of unhalogenated arylcopper reagents with unhalogenated iodoarenes^{8,4}. This may be due to a combination of solvent, steric and electronic effects.

The coupling reactions appear to be affected by the type of perhaloarenes used. No coupling occurs with perchloroarenes. With perfluoro- or perchloroaryl iodides, however, the reaction proceeds smoothly with the selective displacement of iodine. In other systems the organocopper reagents are known to couple with organic bromides, but much less readily^{4,8,13} than with iodides. These observations are in accord with the known reactivities of carbon-halogen bonds.

The formation of aryl iodides (having the aryl group originally attached to the copper reagents) and symmetrical biaryls (Table 1) indicates that the coupling reactions are accompanied by copper-iodine exchange (eq. 3). To know more about the copper-iodine exchange we have studied the reaction between pentachlorophenylcopper and trichloro-2-thienyl iodide in greater detail. The intermediate copper reagent in this reaction, namely trichloro-2-thienylcopper, has been trapped^{14,6} with acetyl chloride to form (trichloro-2-thienyl) methyl ketone. The extent of exchange was found to be significant in pyridine and moderate in THF. No exchange occurred in diethyl ether. This observation agrees with the previous reports^{8,9} that solvents affect the rate of copper-iodine exchange. Furthermore it shows that perhalogenation does not alter the relative importance of the exchange reaction. Since perhalogenation increases considerably the thermal stability of the carbon-copper α -bond^{6,15,16}, involvement of a reaction represented by eq. 2 to form the

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TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF PERHALOARYLCOPPER REAGENTS WITH PERFLUORO- AND PERCHLOROTODARENES

RCu*	R'I	Medium	Temp °C	Time hr	Products, Yields(%)**				
					R-R'	R'-R'	R'I	RI	
0.025 mole	0.025 mole	100 ml							
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu	C ₆ F ₅ I	Dioxan	100	40	46	22	16	7	a trace†
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu	(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)I	Dioxan	100	40	48	—	—	—	—
(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)Cu	C ₆ F ₅ I	Dioxan	100	40	28	3	1	a trace†	a trace†
(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)Cu	C ₆ F ₅ I	Dioxan	100	40	50	44	30	a trace†	a trace†
(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)Cu	(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)I	TMTHF	110	40	40	10	a trace†	2	a trace†
(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)Cu	C ₆ Cl ₅ I	Dioxan	100	40	56	5	10	—	nil
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu	(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)I	Dioxan	100	40	32	15	22	—	—
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu	(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)I	TMTHF	110	40	43	5	9	—	—
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu	(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)I	THF	66	24	8†	—	—	—	15†
C ₆ Cl ₅ Cu;	(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)I	Et ₂ O†	34	24	0†	—	—	—	nil†

* No structures are to be implied from the notation for the copper reagents.

** Based on the starting amount of perhaloarenes employed to prepare the Organometallics.

† By GLC

‡ The copper reagent was prepared from the corresponding lithium reagent and copper(I) iodide. In other cases it was prepared from the corresponding Grignard reagent and copper(I) chloride.

§ A similar reaction when carried out in pyridine at 27° for 24 hr gave, subsequent to reaction with acetyl chloride, R'COCH₃ (24%) and RCOCH₃ (major product). No other products were looked for.

symmetrical biaryls seems to be insignificant. The symmetrical biaryls are probably formed by coupling reactions of the type 4.

It must be noted that neither trichloro-2-thienyllithium nor the corresponding Grignard reagent reacts with iodobenzene to give 2-(phenyl) trichlorothiophene whereas the corresponding copper reagent does^{4,7} in good yield. The unsuitability of organolithium¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and organomagnesium²⁰ reagents for the synthesis of biaryls has been noted before.

In general the unsymmetrical perhalobiaryls have lower melting points than their symmetrical counterparts (Table 2). The unsymmetrical perhalobiaryls undergo halogen-metal exchange reactions with butyllithium; the details of this work will be published later.

described previously^{7,11}. All temperatures quoted are uncorrected. The yields of the unsymmetrical biaryls are based on the starting amount of perhaloarene employed to prepare the perhaloarylcopper reagents.

Preparation of perhaloarylcopper reagents: Pentafluorophenylcopper¹⁴, pentachlorophenylcopper¹⁴, tetrachloro-4-pyridylcopper¹⁴ and trichloro-2-thienylcopper⁷ reagents were prepared in THF as described earlier by reacting pentafluorophenylmagnesium chloride²¹, pentachlorophenylmagnesium chloride²², tetrachloro-4-pyridylmagnesium chloride²³ and trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide¹⁰ respectively, with one equivalent of copper(I) chloride. Pentachlorophenylcopper reagent in ether was prepared from the corresponding lithium

TABLE 2—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA FOR THE UNSYMMETRICAL PERHALOBIARYLS

Biaryl	Linear formulae	M.P.* °C	Element analysed	Found %	Calc %
I	C ₆ F ₅ -C ₆ Cl ₅	127 (Ethanol)	Cl	42.80	42.57
II	C ₆ F ₅ -(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)	78.5 (Pet. eth.†)	Cl	30.00	30.08
III	C ₆ F ₅ -(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)	105-106 (Pet. eth.†)	C	34.27	34.50
IV	C ₆ Cl ₅ -(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)	193-194 (Pet. eth.†)	Cl	64.81	65.08
V	C ₆ Cl ₅ -(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)	222.5-223 (Benzene)	C	28.13	28.40
VI	(4-C ₅ Cl ₄ N)-(2-C ₄ Cl ₃ S)	199 (Benzene)	Cl	61.37	61.68

* For comparison, the m.p. (°C) of the corresponding symmetrical biaryls are reported here: (C₆H₅)₂, 70.5 (ref. 25); (C₆F₅)₂, 68-69 (ref. 26); (C₆Cl₅)₂, 310 (ref. 27); (4-C₅Cl₄N)₂, 226-228 (ref. 28); (2-C₄Cl₃S)₂, 189.5-190 (ref. 29).

† B.p., 60-80°.

Experimental

The general conditions for the organometallic reactions, equipment and material used, were as

reagent²⁴ and copper(I) iodide. For the subsequent coupling reactions the copper reagents were used as prepared in solution, unisolated.

Preparation of perfluoro- and perchloroiodoarenes :

Pentafluoroiodobenzene, b.p. 76-78°/35 mm, pentachloroiodobenzene, m.p. 210°, tetrachloro-4-iodopyridine, m.p. 201-202°, and trichloro-2-iodothiophene, m.p. 49-50° were prepared by iodinating the corresponding perhaloaryl copper reagents with one equivalent of iodine¹¹.

Preparation of perhalogenated unsymmetrical biaryls (Table 1) :

To a perhaloaryl copper reagent (prepared in THF from x moles of an appropriate perhaloaryl-magnesium halide and x moles of copper(I) chloride) was added x moles of a selected perhaloaryl iodide (containing a different perhaloaryl group from that of the copper reagent) in dioxan or 2,2,4,4-tetramethyltetrahydrofuran (TMTHF). The low-boiling

liquids were distilled off and the mixture was heated at 100° (dioxan) or 110° (TMTHF) for a period of 40 hr. The reaction mixture was then hydrolysed with ammonium chloride/aq. ammonia solution and the organic material was collected in benzene. The benzene extract was washed with NH₄Cl/aq. NH₃ until all copper halides were removed, and then washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent distilled. The white solid obtained was generally a mixture of products which were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) and successive recrystallisations from suitable solvents. Table 1 shows the experimental conditions for the preparation of various unsymmetrical perhalobiaryls together with their yields. Only one unsymmetrical biaryl, namely perchloro(2-phenylthiophene) has been prepared under several different experimental conditions ; for the rest, the yields may not be the highest obtainable.

TABLE 3—IR AND MASS SPECTRAL DATA FOR PERHALOGENATED UNSYMMETRICAL BIARYLS

Biaryls	IR(cm ⁻¹)*	Mass spectra†	Mol. wt (calc.) (Cl=35.45)
I	1653, 1597, 1502, 1543, 1344, 1304, 1081, 995, 758, 699, 655	—	—
II	1653, 1597, 1538, 1325, 1316, 1064, 1036, 1027, 978.5, 776, 769, 725	A number of peaks grouped around <i>m/e</i> 354 (M ⁺), 319 (M-Cl) ⁺ and 300 (M-FCl) ⁺ having characteristic isotope patterns for three, two and two Cl-atoms, respectively ; and at 282 and 284 (M-2Cl) ⁺ .	353.53
III	1653, 1595, 1504, 1527, 1493, 1453, 1073, 985, 757, 727, 673, 678	—	—
IV	1359, 1342, 1321, 1311, 714, 692, 660	A number of peaks centered around <i>m/e</i> 436 (M ⁺), 364 (M-2Cl) ⁺ , 329 (M-3Cl) ⁺ , 294 (M-4Cl) ⁺ having characteristic isotope patterns for 8, 6, 5 and 4 Cl-atoms, respectively.	435.80
V	1563, 1548, 1520, 1379, 1355, 1332, 769 and 755	A number of peaks grouped around <i>m/e</i> 465 (M ⁺), 428 (M-Cl) ⁺ , 393 (M-2Cl) ⁺ , 216 (C ₆ Cl ₄ N) ⁺ having characteristic isotope patterns for 9, 8, 7 and 4 Cl-atoms, respectively.	465.20
VI	1550, 1502, 1460, 1399, 1361, 1342, 751, 737, 712	A number of peaks grouped around <i>m/e</i> 403 (M ⁺), 366 (M-Cl) ⁺ , 331 (M-2Cl) ⁺ , 296 (M-3Cl) ⁺ , 216 (C ₆ Cl ₄ N) ⁺ , having the characteristic isotope patterns for 7, 6, 5, 4 and 4 Cl-atoms, respectively.	402.34

* Recorded as either nujol mulls or KBr-pellets using a Perkin-Elmer Model 21 Spectrophotometer.

† Recorded with an Atlas CH₄ Spectrometer.

TABLE 4—ATTEMPTED PREPARATION OF SOME UNSYMMETRICAL POLYHALOBIARYLS

Organometallic reagent*	Aryl halide 0.05 mole	Solvent 100 ml	Reactn temp, °C	Time hr	Recovery of halides, %
(4-C ₆ Cl ₄ N)Cu	C ₆ Cl ₄	THF	65	24	C ₆ Cl ₄ , 96
(4-C ₆ Cl ₄ N)Cu	C ₆ Cl ₄	Dioxan	100	24	C ₆ Cl ₄ , 100
(4-C ₆ Cl ₄ N)Cu	C ₆ Cl ₄ S	THF	65	24	C ₆ Cl ₄ S, 98
(2-C ₆ Cl ₄ S)Li ¹⁰	C ₆ H ₄ I	THF	5-10	8	C ₆ H ₄ I, 85†
(2-C ₆ Cl ₄ S)Mg × ¹⁰	C ₆ H ₄ I	THF	65	12	[(2-C ₆ Cl ₄ S)Ph, 0] ¹⁰

* 0.05 Mole.

† Trichloro-2-iodothiophene (10%, probably formed by lithium-iodine exchange) and 76% of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (formed by the hydrolysis of the lithium reagent during the work-up) were also isolated from this reaction.

Table 2 compares the m.p. of the unsymmetrical perhalobiaryls with those of the symmetrical ones. It also gives the analyses data, and Table 3 the spectral data, for the unsymmetrical perhalobiaryls. Table 4 lists the attempts to prepare some unsymmetrical biaryls under varying conditions.

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References

- H. GILMAN and J. M. STRALEY, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1936, **55**, 821.
- M. NILSSON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 679.
- M. NILSSON and O. WENNERSTRÖM, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 482; M. NILSSON and O. WENNERSTRÖM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 3307.
- M. NILSSON and C. ULLENIUS, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 2379; M. NILSSON and C. ULLENIUS, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1971, **25**, 2428.
- A. E. JUKES, S. S. DUA and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, **24**, 791.
- M. T. RAHMAN and H. GILMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 582.
- M. R. SMITH JR., M. T. RAHMAN and H. GILMAN, *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1971, **1**, 295.
- R. J. DEPASQUALE and C. TAMBORSKI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 1736.
- M. R. SMITH JR. and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1972, **42**, 1.
- M. T. RAHMAN, M. R. SMITH JR., A. F. WEBB and H. GILMAN, *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1970/1971, **1**, 105.
- M. T. RAHMAN and H. GILMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 1018.
- M. T. RAHMAN and H. GILMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 269.
- C. TAMBORSKI, E. J. SOLOSKI and R. J. DEPASQUALE, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1968, **15**, 494.
- A. E. JUKES, S. S. DUA and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1970, **21**, 241.
- A. CAIRNCROSS and W. A. SHEPPARD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 2186.
- S. S. DUA, A. E. JUKES and H. GILMAN, *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1970/1971, **1**, 87.
- R. G. JONES and H. GILMAN, *Org. Reactions*, 1951, **6**, 339.
- H. J. S. WINKLER and H. WINKLER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 964 and 969.
- W. KIRMSER, *Carbene Chemistry*, Academic Press, New York, 1964; G. KÖBRICH, *Angew. Chem. Internat. Ed. Engl.*, 1967, **6**, 41.
- M. S. KHARASCH and O. REINMUTH, *Grignard Reactions of Nonmetallic Substances*, Prentice-Hall, Inc., New York, 1954, Ch. 16.
- A. E. JUKES and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1969, **17**, 145.
- H. GILMAN and SEE-YUEN SIM, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, **7**, 249.
- S. S. DUA and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1968, **12**, 234.
- M. D. RAUSCH, F. E. TIBBETTS and H. B. GORDON, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 493.
- R. FITTIG, *Ann.*, 1862, **121**, 361.
- E. NIELD, R. STEPHENS and J. C. TATLOW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 159.
- F. L. W. VAN ROOSMALEN, *Rec. Trav. Chim., Pays-Bas*, 1934, **53**, 359.
- S. S. DUA and H. GILMAN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1968, **12**, 299.
- O. EBERHARD, *Chem. Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 2385.
- M. R. SMITH JR. and H. GILMAN, *Organometal. Chem. Syn.*, 1971, **1**, 265.